

ESA's Potential Contribution to the EU Space Strategy for Security & Defence (EU SSSD) - From ambition to implementation

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Abstract

ESA welcomes the important step taken with the publication of the EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence (EU SSSD) in 2022, giving the Space domain a key role for security and defence purposes. There is no European Defence without Space. However, the key challenge remains now the concrete implementation of the EU SSSD. In this regard, the European Space Agency can play a significant role as a unique R&D organisation in the space domain in Europe, able to lead complex space architectures and procurement processes involving relevant European companies. In a fierce competitive and aggressive international context, emphasized by the new US administration and a critical international security situation, only a collective and coordinated approach mobilizing all the European Space Actors involved (EU, ESA and their Member States) in their respective fields of responsibilities, existing or already planned capabilities, but also missing capabilities to be identified, the available resources must enable the implementation of the EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence within the tightest deadlines.

Keywords

EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence (EU SSSD), European Space Agency (ESA), resilience, Information Sharing and Analysis Centre (ISAC), accelerator, Galileo, Copernicus, secure connectivity, space safety, cyber security, critical technologies.

1. Introduction

In 2022, EU leaders identified space as a strategic domain in the Strategic Compass (1) and called for an EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence. Building on this political momentum, the Commission and the High Representative have developed the first-ever EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence (EU SSSD) (2).

In a disrupted geopolitical context by the two major powers, Russia and the USA, creating total uncertainty for the future, increasing power competition and intensification of threats, the EU must take action to protect its space assets, defend its interests, deter hostile activities in space and strengthen its strategic posture and autonomy.

In this highly competitive and aggressive international context, only a collective and coordinated approach mobilizing all the European Space Actors involved (EU, ESA and their Member States) in their respective fields of responsibilities, existing or already planned capabilities, but also missing capabilities to be identified, the available resources must enable the implementation of the EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence within the tightest deadlines.

Like any strategy, the next phase is indeed that of its implementation by mobilizing all the good will, the necessary human and financial resources. It is ultimately the political will of the EU and its Member

States to make this strategic work a reality. In this regard, the European Space Agency presents all the skills and experience to contribute significantly to the EU's objectives.

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2. The EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence

The EU SSSD constitutes an important step in awareness and recognition of the contribution of space systems to our daily lives, but also for the vital needs of guaranteeing their use for security and defence purposes.

The EU SSSD identifies the following broad areas of interest and action (2).

The Strategy outlines the counterspace capabilities and main threats in space that put at risk space systems and their ground infrastructure, building on a common definition of the space domain. To increase the common understanding of threats across Member States, the High Representative will prepare a classified annual space threat landscape analysis at EU level, drawing on Member States intelligence. The Strategy proposes as well actions to strengthen the resilience and protection of space systems and services in the EU. For this purpose, the Commission will:

- Consider proposing an EU Space Law to provide a common framework for security, safety, and sustainability in Space that would ensure a consistent and EU-wide approach. That also means to set up an Information Sharing and Analysis Centre (ISAC) in order to raise awareness and facilitate exchange of best practices among commercial and relevant public entities on resilience measures for space capabilities.
- Launch preparatory work to ensure long-term EU autonomous access to space, addressing in particular the security and defence needs.
- Enhance the technological sovereignty of the EU by reducing strategic dependencies and ensuring security of supply for space and defence, in close coordination with the European Defence Agency and the European Space Agency.
- Propose to expand the existing space threat response mechanism which is already used for the protection of Galileo to all space systems and services in the EU.

It calls for the efficient and timely mobilisation of relevant EU tools to respond to space threats. The Strategy proposes appropriate access to space domain awareness information through relevant national space commands to characterize inappropriate behaviours in orbit and protect EU assets. Space exercises, including with partners, will help to test and develop EU response to space threats and to explore solidarity mechanisms.

The Strategy proposes to maximise the use of space for security and defence purposes. The development dual-use services requires to take into account defence requirements when preparing the evolution of the EU space programmes.

The Strategy proposes the launch of two pilots: one for the delivery of initial space domain awareness services building upon capacities of Member States, and another for a new earth observation governmental service as part of the evolution of Copernicus and complementing existing assets.

The strategy also commits to better connect space, defence and security at EU level and ensure synergies and cross-fertilisation, notably in terms of research and development. It proposes concrete measures to foster collaborative work between space and defence start-ups and to enhance skills.

The EU will strengthen its engagement in multilateral fora to partner for responsible behaviours in space and promote norms, rules and principles of responsible behaviours in outer space through concrete and pragmatic steps.

The strategy calls for developing space security dialogues with third countries, in particular with the United States and other likeminded countries. EU-NATO cooperation will also be developed. However, the most reliable partner remains ESA.

3. ESA's analysis of the EU SSSD

ESA's analysis of the EU SSSD highlights the desire for continuity of space activities undertaken over the last decades, but also the need to complement existing capabilities with new services in order to have a complete and coherent space package to contribute to European strategic autonomy. These EU orientations are consistent with or complementary to ESA's activities and missions.

Indeed, the strategy constitutes a defining political and a critical step and pillar to further build the European space policy. Based on the extension of the Galileo model, this is also a critical capability step with the planned implementation of an Earth Observation Governmental Service, but also with the confirmation of the development and deployment of the IRIS2 constellation. The Strategy also strongly confirms the need for a strong space transport capacity, because access to space is clearly a major component of strategic autonomy for the orbiting of all necessary space systems, but also for transport in outer space between planets or celestial bodies, or between artificial objects.

The Space Domain Awareness (SDA) Services identified by the EU SSSD would be of strategic added value to ESA operations & European autonomy. Similarly, partnerships with the United Nations, NATO or third countries that share a similar approach will allow substantial progress, sharing of capabilities and possibly costs. In this partnership context, ESA is recognized for its expertise in the field of technologies promoting EU-ESA synergies. Finally, concerning industrial policy, the EU role in space and defence is an opportunity for competitiveness.

According to the ESA assessment, the SSSD confirms the pertinent ESA's well documented and long-standing position that space infrastructure has a critical bearing on security activities (Agenda 2025 **(3)**, Accelerators **(4)**). ESA is mandated by its Member States to pursue its work on independent access to space, Galileo, Copernicus, secure connectivity, space safety, cyber security, critical technologies for non-dependence. Moreover, ESA's governance and regulatory framework enables it to conduct every type of activities, including of a classified nature which is of high relevance for security and defence-related activities. ESA reaffirms that security in and from space is essential for world stability, the welfare of people and health of our economies and the competitiveness of European industry.

4. The implementation of the EU SSSD

The implementation of the EU SSSD requires the mobilization of all existing, planned space capabilities and the identification of capacity gaps, and a real willingness of EU Member States to contribute, a key condition for success. As such, ESA is the only European space organization capable of leading complex space architectures and soliciting all the most relevant European companies.

For years, ESA has been a clear proponent of taking full advantage of technologies, innovation, and space-based services for security. The growing criticality of space data and technologies in security has now found resonance in key European policy orientations, such as the Strategic Compass, EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence (EU SSSD).

Through its programmes and its space-based data, ESA contributes to a better, safer and more sustainable planet and to the protection of people in Europe and around the globe. In order to avoid further fragmentation and potential duplications in terms of space and security capabilities, the ESA DG has thus proposed to contribute to the implementation of the Strategy, with all of ESA's expertise, in support of its Member States and the EU. Based on its long-standing R&D experience in the field of security-related activities, ESA identified areas and activities where ESA can make a significant contribution and create synergies.

Indeed, ESA programmes offer a comprehensive contribution to Europe's security and world peace and stability. While the breadth of ESA programmes contributing to security, and thus to the EU SSSD, the *main* pillars of this involvement are: Independent access to space, Galileo (5), Copernicus (6), IRIS²(7). Eagle1, SAGA, Civil Security from Space, Earth Explorers, Weather Forecast, ARTES 4S (8), Technologies, Security of Space Infrastructures, the ESTEC Test Centre and the ESTEC secure laboratory, in addition to the ESA-EDA Administrative Arrangement of 2011 and the 2012 ESA-EDA Security Agreement and the role of the ESA Security Office ensures that an harmonised approach is followed in terms of security engineering, certification and accreditation, implementing the ESA security framework across the Agency.

These are but the most noticeable ESA investments in security, which are building blocks and contributions to Europe's security at large, and space security in particular.

Security is strongly linked to the evolution of ESA. In particular, the three Accelerators (R3, PROTECT, Space for a Green Future) directly or indirectly security-related, focus on responding to urgent societal needs, upscaling existing space investments to the next level, with users at the centre of a programmatic evolution that would combine the strengths of ESA, EU, Member States and the private sector. These accelerators could be part of structured dialogue between involved stakeholders.

ESA, thanks to its telecommunications heritage of ARTES Programme, is a natural established leader to develop secure space communication systems based on critical technologies, aiming to satisfy societal needs in terms of resilient and sovereign connectivity for both institutions/governmental entities and citizens/business users.

Moreover, ESA supports the emergence of New Space industry through ARTES programme such as Pioneer, which aims to help space startup companies across the continent in their access to space for in-orbit demonstration and validation.

The EU SSSD is not perceived as an impacting element on ESA telecommunications on-going programmes which mainly rely on the Agency Member-states fundings and support. In particular, the development of commercial systems through public-private partnerships projects, developing New Space is, and shall remain, highly complementary to EU programmes.

This entails that all satellite communication activities that may emerge from the EUSSD's implementation ended to be tailored according to already existing and planned activities, whether in Member States or ESA in order to avoid duplicating effort at continental level. In addition, an institutional competition stemming from uncoordinated policies and programme initiatives needs to

be avoided at all costs: Member States should not have different intermediaries for their funding high-risk technological developments. This inevitable dilution of resources available between European institutions and ESA will be detrimental to the effort of building a world leading European industry in security and defence.

Furthermore, ESA has consistently demonstrated in the navigation domain that it has protected and continues to protect the interests of its Member States and partners. The mechanism that ESA currently has in place through the Security Agreement with the EU has not only never been questioned, but rather lauded for its effectiveness in protecting the interests of EU and its Member States. EU classified information and also sensitive unclassified information, have been zealously protected by ESA and at no moment compromised.

In addition, The EU Space Programme Regulation (9) defines 'Copernicus', as a "civil Earth observation system under civil control, (...) offering geo-information data and services (...) where appropriate, integrating the needs and requirements of security." It further identifies as a specific Copernicus objective "to deliver accurate and reliable Earth observation data, information and services (...) to support the formulation, implementation and monitoring of the Union and its Member States' policies and actions based on user requirements".

To date, within the context of Copernicus and Security, ESA has acted on the following main lines of security related activities, upon request and in cooperation with the European Commission. Nonetheless, to perform sensitive or classified activities, including protection of data and interest of its Member States, a secure context must be guaranteed.

5. The Role of ESA

ESA is a civil R&D organisation. That means that ESA designs and develops space capabilities to meet various needs, and although ESA validates and demonstrates services, ESA does not play an operational role. This responsibility befalls upon national and regional actors who can best determine how they will use these space assets to serve their interests. Regardless, a tailored regulatory framework enables the delivery of such assets for its constituencies. The ESA Convention and its regulations, as well as the legal instruments binding it to the EU, guarantee the protection of the security interests of its Member States and those of its partners.

Security by design has always been ESA's approach based, in particular on policies, regulations and technological expertise: ESA can undertake any programme, at any level of sensitivity or even classification. This was clearly recognised in the Resolution by ESA's Ministerial Council in November 2023 during which Member States affirmed "the role of ESA in (...) delivering security-relevant benefits to its Member States and partners through technical excellence and its unique or leading capabilities in response to stakeholder requirements." Member States furthermore "[recognised] the Agency's internal security governance enabling it to securely manage its activities and programmes."

ESA thus ensures a comprehensive security management approach:

Credibility relies on reliability, in security-sensitive domains even more than in non-security critical areas. The reliability of the ESA security service is already today ensured by an elaborate internal security framework, with the Council-approved ESA Security Regulations and the ESA Security Authority, which is responsible, on behalf of the Director General, for the coordination of ESA Security Management activities.

The ESA security management function, delegated to the ESA Security Office, distributed across all ESA Directorates, and exercised in synergy with the security bodies of the Member States, ensures a centralized and transversal security management approach through, *inter alia*, a unique Point of contact for internal and external stakeholders and a unique, coordinated Security Strategy for Security from Space. In addition to the mechanisms provided for in the Convention (10) and programme-specific legal frameworks, this set-up is a pivotal element to the proper protection of the EU security objectives.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, ESA welcomes the important step taken with the publication of the EU SSSD: with the evolution of technology, its more widespread availability, governments, and institutions need to rethink and update our structures to deliver better adapted security systems to users, in a controlled and secure manner, fully respecting national sovereignty.

The Strategy is a defining political step that will contribute positively to making Europe a better equipped strategic player. It is furthermore a critical capability step with the Earth Observation Governmental Service, the extension of the Galileo model, IRIS2, the confirmation of orientations that ESA has already begun in space transportation, while Space Domain Awareness services would be of strategic added value to all space operations, including those of ESA.

ESA has been proposing and urging for long, such as accelerating synergies in space and security, a shared understanding of space threats, the resilience and protection of space systems and services which obviously also affect ESA assets and our Member States investments.

ESA has the regulatory framework (including sensitive / classified projects) and technical *savoir faire* to accompany the EU in its new ambitions and to ensure the protection of the security interest of the EU and EU/ESA Member States.

Security can be a defining factor of ESA's future evolution: because of the increasing relevance and criticality of space in crisis response combined with the wider availability of such services, we will need to tackle a governance evolution regarding the control – which some call “sovereignty” - over some specific technologies relevant to security operations, as well as the development in cooperation of some capabilities that have up until today only been considered as strictly national.

During CM22, Member States have agreed to programmes covering independent access to space, Galileo, Copernicus, secure connectivity, space safety, cyber security, critical technologies for non-dependence.

Europe must better coordinate its space capability developments and cooperatively deliver those space services that Member States require for their domestic security and at their borders. ESA is not the sole architect of such evolutions, only a part of this evolution, as the distinction between civil and defence, or public and commercial domains become increasingly irrelevant and as we witness a growing acceptance that new synergies must be built as part of a consistent and comprehensive approach towards space and security, allowing a more efficient use of funding, public and private, concentrating on user needs addressing major challenges, shared by all on Earth.

The Accelerators form a solid basis to deepen the dialogue with EU institutions on how to better synchronise and consolidate fragmented space and security efforts in Europe.

Security *in* and *from* space is essential to the welfare of people, robustness of our economies and the competitiveness of European industry.

The Paris Ministerial Council in November 2022 invited “the strengthening of ESA’s ability to serve its Member States and cooperate with its partners, including the European Union, in the context of security, by reinforcing European industry and its competitiveness, fostering exchange and dialogue with security actors of Member States, and developing technologies and capabilities to better protect Europe and its citizens from crises and risks.” It is precisely in this spirit that ESA proposes to engage the EU in a constructive space and security dialogue, that ought to not only “recognise the sovereignty of the Member States in the field of security” but also the roles and added value of both the EU and ESA.

7. References

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Short Biography:

Pascal LEGAI is currently the Senior Security Adviser to ESA DG. He has a military background (Major General in the French Air and Space Force). He acquired experience mainly in the fields of geography, imagery intelligence, international relations, Space and Security issues. He has extensive international experience in the geospatial information domain. Before joining ESA, he was Director of the EU Satellite Centre, an imagery analysis centre, based near Madrid, Spain, providing Geospatial Intelligence (GEOINT) and Imagery Intelligence (IMINT) products and services to support the EU external action. He has a PhD in International Relations, a qualification as Research Director, a law degree, several Master degrees in Imagery Processing, Computer Sciences, in History, in Irish Civilization, in Mathematics. He is an aerospace engineer and has also an Engineer Diploma in the field of the geographic sciences.